

OPTIMAL RELAXATION OF STRESS CONCENTRATIONS IN ADAPTIVE LAMINATED COMPOSITES WITH PIEZOELECTRIC ACTUATORS

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ABSTRACT

Optimal relaxation of stress concentrations in laminated composites by using piezoelectric actuators is considered. An adaptive structure model is presented, in which the substrate is a laminated composite with a circular hole and actuators are bonded to its surfaces around the hole. In order to examine the performance of the adaptive structure, finite element analysis incorporated with optimization is carried out. The optimization problem is formulated on the basis of the maximum stress criterion. Typical numerical results are shown for optimally applied voltage to each piezoelectric actuator to prevent failure in unidirectional, cross-ply and angle-ply laminates subjected to uniaxial tensile loading.

INTRODUCTION

Smart structures using induced strain actuators such as piezoelectrics and shape-memory alloys may be expected to achieve active damage control. Activation of these induced strain actuators will generate new stress and strain fields resulting in changes in the stress and strain distributions of the structures, and be possible to reduce the stress concentrations and the stress intensity factors at crack tips in the structures. As a result, the damage initiation and crack propagation in structures in service, such as airplanes, will be able to prevented.

Rogers et al. [1] presented some important applications of induced strain actuators in active damage control. They mentioned that piezoelectric actuators have the capability to induce various amounts of strain, therefore, it is possible to reduce the stress concentrations in plates with a hole under varying external load conditions by distributing the piezoelectric actuators in high stress regions, such as around the hole, in advance. For this application, the authors [2] and Sensharma et al. [3] investigated the optimal relaxation of stress concentrations in an isotropic plate with a hole by using piezoelectric actuators and applied induced strains, respectively.

The objective of this study is to consider optimal relaxation of stress concentrations in laminated composites by using piezoelectric actuators. Finite element analysis incorporated with optimization is performed. Typical numerical results are shown for optimally applied voltage to each piezoelectric actuator to prevent failure in unidirectional, cross-ply and angle-ply laminates

subjected to uniaxial tensile loading.

ADAPTIVE STRUCTURE MODEL

An adaptive structure for numerical analysis is presented in Fig. 1, in which piezoelectric actuators are bonded perfectly to the surfaces of an infinite laminated composite with a circular hole. The laminated composites as the substrata are symmetric laminates with arbitrary laminate

Cross section A-A

Figure 1. Adaptive structure made of a laminated composite and piezoelectric actuators.

Figure 2. Rectangular coordinate systems.

configurations. Fig. 2 shows two rectangular coordinate systems used, of which the L -axis denotes the fiber direction of each ply and angle Θ is the ply orientation angle.

The arrow in Fig. 1 indicates the poling direction of the piezoelectric actuator. If an electric field is applied across the actuator against the poling direction, as can be seen in Fig. 1, the actuator will expand in its radial direction. If the field is reversed, the actuator will generate contraction deformation. In general, it is known that piezoelectrics have nonlinearity in the relation between applied electric field and resulting actuation strain [4]. However, we assume the ideal linear relation in this study. Then, the actuation strain in the x - y plane, Λ , is related to the applied electric field V/t_A in the following form:

$$\Lambda = d_{31} \frac{V}{t_A} \quad (1)$$

where d_{31} is called the piezoelectric constant and t_A is thickness of the actuator. By using such actuation strains generated by all pairs of the actuators symmetrically located with respect to the neutral plane of the laminated composites, it is possible to reduce higher stresses around the hole under varying externally applied stress conditions. As a result, the failure load of the laminated composites is improved.

FORMULATION OF OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

Let us try maximizing the failure stress resultants of the laminated composites subjected to a given state of stress resultants (N_x, N_y, N_{xy}) by activating all piezoelectric actuators. In this section, the formulation of the optimization problem is made to seek the maximum value of the stress resultants (N_x^F, N_y^F, N_{xy}^F) and the optimally applied voltage to each piezoelectric actuator.

It is well known that individual plies within laminated composites have highly directionally dependent strengths. Therefore, when the failures of such unidirectional plies are considered under the plane stress state, three stresses in the principal material directions are needed, that is to say, the longitudinal stress σ_L , the transverse stress σ_T and the longitudinal-transverse shear stress τ_{LT} . Here, the stresses in the principal material directions in the k -th ply at an arbitrary point $j(x,y)$ within the laminate, $\sigma_{Lj_k}, \sigma_{Tj_k}, \tau_{LTj_k}$, are given by combining the stresses due to the applied stress resultants, $\sigma_{Lj_k}^*, \sigma_{Tj_k}^*, \tau_{LTj_k}^*$, and those due to the actuation strains of individual actuators, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{Lj_k} &= \sigma_{Lj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^L V_i \\ \sigma_{Tj_k} &= \sigma_{Tj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^T V_i \\ \tau_{LTj_k} &= \tau_{LTj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^{LT} V_i \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $g_{ij_k}^L, g_{ij_k}^T, g_{ij_k}^{LT}$ are stress components in the principal material directions in the k -th ply at the point $j(x,y)$ when the i -th actuator is applied the unit positive voltage (then, the actuator generates extensional strain in the x - y plane, d_{31}), V_i is applied voltage to the i -th actuator and n is the number of the actuators.

In this study, the following maximum stress criterion is used,

$$\begin{aligned} -F_L &\leq \sigma_L \leq F_L \\ -F_T &\leq \sigma_T \leq F_T \\ -F_{LT} &\leq \tau_{LT} \leq F_{LT} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where F_L and $F_{L'}$ are the longitudinal tensile and compressive strengths, F_T and $F_{T'}$ the transverse tensile and compressive strengths and F_{LT} the longitudinal-transverse shear strength.

In order to maximize the failure stress resultants (N_x^F, N_y^F, N_{xy}^F) subjected to a given state of stress resultants (N_x, N_y, N_{xy}), the ratio R defined as the following equation should be maximized [5].

$$\begin{aligned} N_x^F &= RN_x \\ N_y^F &= RN_y \\ N_{xy}^F &= RN_{xy} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

When the adaptive laminated composite is subjected to the failure stress resultants (N_x^F, N_y^F, N_{xy}^F), the stresses in the principal material directions in the k -th ply at the point $j(x,y)$ in the laminate are given by using Eqns (2) and (4), as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{Lj_k} &= R \sigma_{Lj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^L V_i \\ \sigma_{Tj_k} &= R \sigma_{Tj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^T V_i \\ \tau_{LTj_k} &= R \tau_{LTj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^{LT} V_i \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Thus, the optimization problem to seek the maximum value of the ratio R and optimally applied voltages to individual actuators, V_i , can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{maximize } R \\ &\text{subject to } \left. \begin{aligned} -F_{L'} &\leq R \sigma_{Lj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^L V_i \leq F_L \\ -F_{T'} &\leq R \sigma_{Tj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^T V_i \leq F_T \\ -F_{LT} &\leq R \tau_{LTj_k}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n g_{ij_k}^{LT} V_i \leq F_{LT} \end{aligned} \right\} (j = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, l) \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where R and V_i are design variables. Finite element method with three-node triangular elements based on the classical lamination theory is used for stress analysis. As can be seen in Eqn (6), the optimization problem is the linear programming problem, and the optimal solutions can be easily obtained.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

In order to examine the performance of the adaptive structure, numerical analysis incorporated with optimization was carried out for laminated composites subjected to uniaxial tensile loading $(0, N, 0)$. The laminated composites are E-glass/epoxy laminates with five different laminate configurations such as $[0^\circ]$, $[45^\circ]$, $[90^\circ]$ (unidirectional composites), $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ (cross-ply laminate) and $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ (angle-ply laminate). The volume fraction of glass fibers, V_f , is 72%. Mechanical properties of the E-glass/epoxy lamina [6] are listed in Table 1. As piezoelectric actuators, lead zirconate titanate (PZT) ceramics are used, of which Young's modulus is $E=63\text{GPa}$, Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.3$ and piezoelectric constant $d_{31}=190 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m/V}$, respectively [7]. The thicknesses of the actuators and the substrate are $t_A=0.25 \text{ mm}$ and $t_p=2.0 \text{ mm}$,

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the E-glass/epoxy lamina ($V_f = 72\%$).

Elastic constant	GPa	Strength	GPa
E_L	60.7	F_L	1.2894
E_T	24.8	$F_{L'}$	0.8205
G_{LT}	11.99	F_T	0.0460
ν_{LT}	0.23	$F_{T'}$	0.1744
		F_{LT}	0.0448

Figure 3. Failure stress resultant for five laminate configurations.

respectively. In optimization procedure, applied voltage to each actuator, V_i , has no constraint.

Fig. 3 shows the failure stress resultant N^F for five laminate configurations. In the figure, the percentages of the improvement ratio to failure in the case of no-actuator are presented. The cross-ply laminate marks the highest improvement ratio 71.7% out of five laminates. The results of circumferential stresses on the hole boundary and optimally applied voltage to each piezoelectric actuator for the cross-ply laminate are shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 shows the failure initiation points for the cross-ply laminate. In general, the failure initiation of laminated composites with a hole under uniaxial tensile loading is dominated by the transverse tensile strength F_T and the shear strength F_{LT} . However, the mode of the failure initiation for the cross-ply laminate after optimization is that of the transverse tension in the 0° ply only.

CONCLUSIONS

Finite element analysis incorporated with optimization has been performed to demonstrate optimal relaxation of stress concentrations in laminated composites by using piezoelectric actuators. The optimization problem was formulated on the basis of the maximum stress criterion. The laminated composites used in numerical analysis were E-glass/epoxy laminates with a hole and with five different laminate configurations such as $[0^\circ]$, $[45^\circ]$, $[90^\circ]$ (unidirectional composites), $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ (cross-ply laminate) and $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ (angle-ply laminate). As the numerical results for uniaxial tensile loading, the cross-ply laminate marked the highest improvement ratio of 71.7% on failure stress resultant out of the five laminates. The optimally

Figure 4. Circumferential stresses on the hole boundary and optimally applied voltage to the piezoelectric actuators for $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_5$ laminate.

Figure 5. Failure initiation points for $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_5$ laminate.

applied voltage to each piezoelectric actuator and failure initiation points for the cross-ply laminate have also been shown in the figures.

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